

EVALUATION OF THE TRUE ZETA-POTENTIAL OF HIDE AND LEATHER DIAPHRAGMS

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The electro-osmotic flow of water through membranes of hide and leather in equilibrium with dilute solutions of NaCl of constant p_{H} , but of varying specific conductivity, has been studied. The apparent electrokinetic potential ζ_a , calculated from the experimental data, using the Smoluchowski equation, has been found to vary with the specific conductance, K , in bulk of the electrolyte solutions used, according to the equation:

$$\frac{I}{G} = \frac{I}{\zeta} + m \cdot \frac{I}{K}$$

where m is a constant and ζ represents the true electrokinetic potential. The significance of the results obtained has been discussed.

The electrokinetic or ζ -potential, evaluated from electro-osmotic experiments, may not always represent the true value due to factors like surface conductivity (Bikerman, *Disc. Faraday Soc.*, 1940, 154; Rutgers, *ibid.*, p. 69).

Experiments have therefore been undertaken to ascertain if the true ζ -potential of hide and leather diaphragms in solutions, having constant p_{H} but varying conductivity, effected by changing the concentration of added sodium chloride, a neutral electrolyte having no specific affinity for protein groups, can be determined by the electro-osmotic method. The results obtained are recorded in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

Samples selected at random from pieces of lined goat skin and of formaldehyde-, vegetable, and chrome-tanned leathers were used as diaphragms. These were washed free of electrolytes, using conductivity water. The chrome-tanned leather was, however, neutralised in dilute borax prior to washing; this was necessary, as otherwise it was difficult to obtain an equilibrium solution of constant p_{H} with the chrome-tanned leather in very dilute borate buffers.

Electro-osmotic Experiments

A simple cell was devised for measuring the rate of electro-osmotic flow through hide or leather membranes. The cell consisted of two bored rubber blocks in between which the membrane was held watertight by means of two wooden frames, joined by four screws. The two limbs of the electro-osmotic cell, forming a U-tube together, passed through the bores in the rubber blocks till they came in contact with the leather from the two sides.

The two limbs were filled with the solution, against which the ζ -potential was to be determined and in which the membrane had previously been soaked to equilibrium. The liquid in the limbs was continuous through a narrow flow tube,

so that there was no difference in hydrostatic pressure between the two limbs and also the liquid passing through the membrane during electro-osmosis did not generate any appreciable difference in hydrostatic pressure. The electro-osmotic flow was measured by noting the movement of a small air-bubble (0.5 cm) which was introduced into the flow tube while setting up the apparatus with the help of two three-way stop-cocks; the rate of flow was calculated from the values of the internal cross-section of the tube and the distance moved by the air-bubble in unit time. The flow tube itself was filled with conductivity water and kept horizontal. In this arrangement, the diameter of the tube employed in the cell was small and the bulging of the membrane did not occur.

The flow tube, stop-cocks, as well as the glass parts of the cell were kept in chromic acid prior to experimentation in order to remove grease. This was necessary for ensuring smooth movement of the air-bubble in the flow tube.

The electrical circuit for the electro-osmotic experiment was quite simple. The supply from 220 volt DC mains was dropped to a constant voltage of 105 by using a VR 105 electronic valve. The voltage was applied to the two electrodes dipped into the limbs of the cell through one constant and another adjustable resistances, a milliammeter and a commutator. The resistance was so adjusted as to give a current strength of not more than 10 millamps as otherwise, at the concentrations of the electrolytes in some of the experiments, there was much electrolysis and evolution of gas bubbles which interfered with the measurement.

The experiments were conducted at the room temperature, which was always noted, since this was necessary for securing the viscosity of the liquid at this temperature.

Pieces of goat skin or leather were soaked in 250 c.c. of dilute buffer or dilute acid for 5-7 days for the attainment of equilibrium (*i.e.*, till p_H became constant). Soaked pieces were then fitted up in the cell to act as diaphragms and the electro-osmotic velocity measured. ζ_a was calculated using the value of bulk specific conductivity, K .

After the first experiment, a few drops of dilute sodium chloride solution were added to the soaking solution for obtaining a higher specific conductivity without changing the p_H ; the solution was quickly allowed to flow several times through the membrane fitted in the cell, mechanically or under the influence of an electrical field. The limbs were filled up with the solution containing NaCl and the ζ_a obtained again at a higher bulk specific conductivity of the equilibrium solution.

The p_H of the solution was measured by a glass electrode after each determination of flow, and the p_H did not change more than 0.1 unit throughout the whole range of conductivities studied. The apparent ζ_a potential was calculated by using the Smoluchowski equation:

$$\zeta_a = \frac{4\pi\eta KV}{iD} \times (100)^2$$

where η = coeff. of viscosity, K = sp. conductivity, and D = the dielectric constant of the solution in contact with the diaphragm; V = volume of liquid passing through dia-

phragm per sec. and i = the current strength. The true ζ -potential was then evaluated from the apparent ζ_a by using the following equation in which the surface conductivity correction was introduced :

$$\frac{i}{\zeta_a} = \frac{i}{\zeta} + m \frac{i}{K} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where m is a constant which includes sp. surface conductivity (Ghosh, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1953, 49, 1475; this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 69).

The results of the determination of ζ -potential at a particular p_H and different specific conductivities are recorded in Table I (A-F). ζ represents the corrected value of ζ_a .

TABLE I

Electro-osmosis through variously tanned leather.

K (mho cm^{-1}).	ζ_a (mv)	$1/K$.	$1/\zeta_a \times 10$.	ζ (from graph).	K (mho cm^{-1}).	ζ_a (mv)	$1/K$.	$1/\zeta_a \times 10$	ζ (from graph).
A. Goatskin at p_H 7.35 in borate buffer.					B. Chrome-tanned leather in borate buffer at p_H 6.6.				
8.22×10^{-5}	2.73	12170	3.67		4.29×10^{-5}	18.7	23310	5.35	
3.66×10^{-4}	6.33	2730	1.58	9.52 mv	5.90×10^{-5}	2.38	16940	4.23	7.81 mv
7.63×10^{-4}	7.23	1311	1.38		4.32×10^{-4}	6.14	2317	1.63	
1.48×10^{-3}	7.19	677.4	1.39		1.66×10^{-3}	6.74	600.9	1.48	
C. Vegetable-tanned leather at p_H 3.8.					D. Vegetable-tanned leather at p_H 4.3.				
1.44×10^{-4}	3.70	8772	2.70		3.98×10^{-5}	3.87	25140	2.58	
4.46×10^{-4}	6.10	2240	1.64	9.43	6.97×10^{-5}	5.40	14350	1.85	
1.43×10^{-3}	8.72	699.3	1.15		5.60×10^{-4}	9.70	1784	1.05	11.78
3.04×10^{-3}	8.90	328.9	1.12		1.74×10^{-3}	11.69	573.7	0.855	
					3.44×10^{-3}	11.74	290.7	0.855	
E. Formaldehyde-tanned leather at p_H 6.7.					F. Formaldehyde-tanned leather at p_H 7.4.				
4.54×10^{-4}	2.41	2200	4.15		4.16×10^{-4}	3.41	2406	2.93	
6.17×10^{-4}	2.74	1620	3.65	4.61	5.97×10^{-4}	3.98	1675	2.51	7.14
1.00×10^{-3}	3.48	997.8	2.87		1.18×10^{-3}	5.57	850	1.79	

It will be seen that for a particular membrane at a constant p_H , the observed potential ζ_a increases with K , and approaches a limiting value when the specific conductivity is above 1×10^{-3} mho/cm.

DISCUSSION

Previous experimental work on the electrokinetic behaviour of proteins, cellulose etc. dealt mainly with the effect of ionic strength on the cataphoretic mobility or the ζ_a potential. While an increase in the value of the ζ_a potential has been obtained with cellulose (Briggs, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1928, 32, 641) at very low concentrations of salts like NaCl, the result is not conclusive in the case of proteins.

Bikerman and also Rutgers (*loc. cit.*) suggested that the rise in ζ_a at low electrolyte concentration was spurious and was due to surface conductivity effect. Ghosh and

Ghosh (this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 649) have shown that the published data on the streaming potential and surface conductivity of diaphragms constituted of cellulose fibres are again well represented by an equation of the type :

$$i/\zeta_s = i/\zeta + \alpha \frac{K_p - K}{K} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where α is a constant, K_p , the specific conductivity of the solution inside the diaphragm and K , its bulk specific conductivity. The constant α varies for different diaphragms, depending upon the evenness and tightness of packing and specific volumes of the materials.

Diaphragms of leather or hide, having a compact weaving of fibres not destroyed by handling, are therefore very suitable for electro-osmotic measurements, since α does not change during experimentation. If within a small range of electrolyte concentration at the same pH , the true ζ -potential and surface conductance are assumed constant, for a particular membrane, the equation (2) for surface conductance assumes the form of equation (1), referred to already, so that a plot of i/ζ_s against i/K should be a straight line, the intercept of which on the i/ζ_s axis should give the value of true ζ at that pH .

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

FIG. 4

Figures 1-4 show that such a linear relation has been obtained in nearly all the cases investigated. The true ζ at each p_n has been given in the last column of the table (A-F).

From the table we see that the true values of ζ differs widely from the observed values of ζ_o . However, the effect of surface conductivity becomes small when the bulk conductivity of the solution is above 10^{-3} mho/cm, as can be seen from the table.

It is to be noted that the linear relationship envisaged in equation (1) holds only so long as true ζ and the specific conductance remain constant at a given p_n , even on the addition of NaCl. These two conditions are evidently fulfilled when the concentration of NaCl added is small.

The method of evaluating true ζ developed in this paper may be utilised for the determination of isoelectric point of structured hide or leather.

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Corrigendum

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Page 675, Line 21

Read 5.6×10^3 for 5.6.